

Oral Health Status of Latvian Adolescents Aged 12 and 15 Years: A Cross-Sectional Epidemiological Study

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Abstract

Aim: To assess caries prevalence, severity, and associated factors among Latvian adolescents aged 12 and 15 years, and to describe periodontal health and other oral conditions.

Methods: Cross-sectional study conducted during the 2022/2023 school year. We examined 6th and 9th grade students from 58 schools selected through stratified cluster sampling. Ten calibrated dentists (kappa 0.67–0.80) assessed caries using merged ICDAS criteria, periodontal health using BPE, and other conditions following WHO recommendations. Data analysis used R with generalized logistic regression.

Results: We examined 3,128 adolescents (1,557 aged 12 years; 1,571 aged 15 years). Response rates were 65% and 56%, respectively. Caries prevalence at D₃MFT level was 66.3% at age 12 and 83.5% at age 15. Mean D₃MFT was 2.3 [SD 2.5] at age 12 and 4.4 [SD 3.9] at age 15. Only 13.9% of 12-year-olds and 6.7% of 15-year-olds were caries-free. Healthy periodontium was present in 28% of 12-year-olds and 26% of 15-year-olds. Visible plaque was associated with higher caries (IRR 1.49 [95%CI 1.45, 1.53]) and gingivitis (OR 6.17 [95%CI 5.14, 7.45]). Rural residence, infrequent toothbrushing, unknown fluoride content in toothpaste, and daily sugary drink consumption were associated with higher caries severity. Molar-incisor hypomineralization affected 4–5%, fluorosis 5%, and dental trauma 6–7% of adolescents.

Conclusions: Latvian adolescents have high caries prevalence and poor periodontal health. Oral hygiene practices remain inadequate. Policy interventions should address preventive care access, fluoride toothpaste availability, and dietary habits.

Keywords: dental caries, adolescents, oral health, epidemiology, Latvia, ICDAS

Introduction

Oral diseases affect 3.5 billion people worldwide (GBD 2017 Oral Disorders Collaborators et al., 2020). Dental caries remains the most prevalent condition, despite being preventable through established interventions (Kidd et al., 2020). The European Region has the highest caries prevalence among WHO regions, with substantial variation between countries (WHO, 2023).

Latvia lacks recent population-level data on adolescent oral health. The 2016 epidemiological survey found caries prevalence of 79% at D₃MFT level among 12-year-olds (Maldupa et al., 2020). The WHO recommends repeating oral health surveys every 5–6 years to monitor trends and inform policy (WHO, 2013).

This study aimed to assess caries prevalence, severity, and associated factors among Latvian adolescents aged 12 and 15 years, and to describe periodontal health and other oral conditions.

Methods

Study design and setting

We conducted a cross-sectional study during the 2022/2023 school year (October 2022 to May 2023) in Latvia. The study received ethical approval from the Riga Stradiņš University Research Ethics Committee (No. 6-1/16/6, 26 November 2020).

Participants

The target population was 6th and 9th grade students in Latvian general education schools. We used stratified cluster sampling with schools as the primary sampling unit. Stratification variables were region (Riga, Pierīga, Zemgale, Vidzeme, Kurzeme, Latgale), school location (republican city, other city, rural), and instruction language. We excluded special education institutions and schools with fewer than 8 students per grade.

Sample size was calculated to detect caries prevalence with 95% confidence. We selected 58 schools proportional to student distribution across strata. Inclusion criteria were: parental consent, child assent, and ASA I health status. Exclusion criteria were: incomplete examination, age outside target range, or subsequent withdrawal.

Clinical examination

Ten dentists underwent training and calibration. Inter-examiner agreement (kappa) ranged from 0.67 to 0.80 at ICDAS₁ level. Examinations occurred in school settings with portable equipment. Children were examined supine with headlamp illumination (350 lm). Supervised toothbrushing preceded examination to facilitate caries detection.

We assessed caries using merged ICDAS criteria at three thresholds: enamel caries (D₁, ICDAS 1–2), enamel-dentin junction caries (D₃, ICDAS 3–4), and dentin caries (D₅, ICDAS 5–6). Periodontal health was assessed using BPE index. Dental erosion was assessed using TWI, fluorosis using Dean criteria, and other conditions following WHO recommendations (WHO, 2013).

A structured questionnaire collected demographic information (sex, age, residence, language spoken at home) and behavioural factors (toothbrushing frequency, fluoride toothpaste use, sugary food and drink consumption, dental visit frequency, tobacco use).

Statistical analysis

Data were analysed using R software (R Core Team, 2023) with tidyverse packages (Wickham, 2017). We calculated prevalence, means, and standard deviations for caries indices. We used generalized logistic regression for risk indicator analysis, adjusting for clustering by school. We report incidence rate ratios (IRR) with 95% confidence intervals for caries severity (D₃MFS) and odds ratios (OR) for periodontal disease (BPE >0).

Results

Study population

We examined 3,943 students, of whom 3,128 met age criteria (1,557 aged 12 years; 1,571 aged 15 years). Response rates were 65% for 6th graders and 56% for 9th graders. Girls comprised 51% of participants.

Caries prevalence

Caries prevalence at D₁ level (including enamel lesions) was 86.1% at age 12 and 93.3% at age 15. At D₃ level (cavitated lesions), prevalence was 66.3% at age 12 and 83.5% at age 15. At D₅ level (dentin involvement), prevalence was 55.6% at age 12 and 76.3% at age 15.

Only 13.9% of 12-year-olds and 6.7% of 15-year-olds were caries-free at D₁ level.

Caries severity

Mean D₃MFT was 2.3 [SD 2.5] at age 12 and 4.4 [SD 3.9] at age 15. Mean D₁MFT was 5.3 [SD 4.6] at age 12 and 8.3 [SD 5.7] at age 15. The Significant Caries Index (SiC) at D₃ level was 5.3 at age 12 and 9.3 at age 15, indicating a subgroup with high disease burden.

Girls had higher caries severity than boys ($p < 0.001$). Regional variation was present: Riga and Pierīga had the lowest D₃MFT (1.6–2.1 at age 12), while Latgale and Zemgale had the highest (2.8–3.0 at age 12).

Caries risk indicators

Generalized logistic regression identified several factors associated with higher D₃MFS (Table 2). Rural residence was associated with 55–62% higher caries severity compared to Riga (IRR 1.55–1.62). Brushing teeth less than twice daily was associated with 7–8% higher severity. Visible plaque was associated with 49% higher severity (IRR 1.49 [95%CI 1.45, 1.53]). Unknown fluoride content in toothpaste was associated with 16% higher severity (IRR 1.16 [95%CI 1.12, 1.19]). Daily sugary drink consumption was associated with 9% higher severity (IRR 1.09 [95%CI 1.05, 1.12]).

Attending a dentist or hygienist at least yearly was associated with slightly lower caries at D₃ level (IRR 0.96 [95%CI 0.93, 0.99]).

Periodontal health

Healthy periodontium (BPE = 0) was present in 28% of 12-year-olds and 26% of 15-year-olds. Gingival bleeding was present in 38% and 37%, calculus in 33% and 37%, respectively. Periodontal pockets (≥ 4 mm) were rare ($< 0.1\%$).

Visible plaque was strongly associated with gingivitis (OR 6.17 [95%CI 5.14, 7.45]). Daily sweet consumption was associated with 33% higher odds of gingivitis (OR 1.33 [95%CI 1.12, 1.58]). Infrequent dental visits were associated with poorer periodontal health (OR 1.26 [95%CI 1.01, 1.58]).

Behavioural factors

Only 45% of 12-year-olds and 51% of 15-year-olds brushed teeth twice daily. Visible plaque was present in approximately 50%. Only 40% of 12-year-olds and 46% of 15-year-olds knew their toothpaste contained adequate fluoride (≥ 1000 ppm). Approximately 56% and 48% did not know their toothpaste's fluoride content.

Daily sugary food consumption was reported by 70% of 12-year-olds and 73% of 15-year-olds. Daily sugary drink consumption was reported by 64% in both age groups. Tobacco use was reported by 0.9% of 12-year-olds and 12.4% of 15-year-olds.

Other oral conditions

Molar-incisor hypomineralization (MIH) affected 5% of 12-year-olds and 4% of 15-year-olds. Dental fluorosis affected 4.5% and 4.8%, respectively, mostly in very mild forms.

Dental trauma history was present in 6.4% of 12-year-olds and 7.4% of 15-year-olds. Upper central incisors were most commonly affected. Erosion affected $< 1\%$ at age 12 and 1% at age 15. Abrasion/attrition affected 0.6% and 2.4%, respectively.

Oral mucosal lesions were present in 2.6% of 12-year-olds and 2.0% of 15-year-olds. Cheilitis (1.6% and 0.8%) and ulcerative lesions (0.8% each) were most common.

Orthodontic treatment experience (current or past) was reported by 11.5% of 12-year-olds and 18.8% of 15-year-olds.

Sealant use

Only 6–7% of adolescents had at least one sealant. However, 64% of 12-year-olds and 74% of 15-year-olds had enamel lesions on occlusal surfaces indicating sealant indication.

Discussion

Main findings

This study found high caries prevalence among Latvian adolescents: 66% at age 12 and 84% at age 15 at D₃MFT level. Mean D₃MFT was 2.3 and 4.4, respectively. Only 14% of 12-year-olds were caries-free. Periodontal health was poor, with gingivitis present in over 70%. Oral hygiene practices were inadequate: only half brushed twice daily, and most did not know their toothpaste's fluoride content.

Comparison with other populations

Caries prevalence in Latvia exceeds European averages. The WHO European Region report indicates mean DMFT of 1.9 at age 12 [REFERENCE NEEDED]. Latvia's figure of 2.3 places it among higher-burden countries. Neighbouring Lithuania reported MIH prevalence of 9.7% in children aged 7–9 years (Jasulaityte, Veerkamp and Weerheijm, 2007), higher than our finding of 4–5%, though age differences limit comparison.

Risk indicators

Visible plaque emerged as the strongest modifiable risk indicator for both caries and gingivitis. This finding confirms that oral hygiene remains central to disease prevention. The association between rural residence and higher caries suggests access barriers or lifestyle differences requiring targeted interventions.

The finding that most adolescents did not know their toothpaste's fluoride content is concerning. Effective caries prevention requires fluoride concentrations of at least 1000 ppm (Walsh et al., 2019). Public education about toothpaste selection and product labelling may improve fluoride exposure.

The low sealant prevalence (6–7%) despite high indication (64–74%) represents a missed prevention opportunity. Sealants effectively prevent and arrest caries on occlusal surfaces (Wright et al., 2016). Their inclusion in state-funded dental care could reduce treatment need.

Limitations

This study has limitations. The response rate (56–65%) was lower than desired, and school refusals (24%) may introduce selection bias. Children from more health-conscious families may be over-represented, suggesting true prevalence could be higher. The cross-sectional design prevents causal inference. Self-reported behaviours may be subject to social desirability bias.

Conclusions

Latvian adolescents have high caries prevalence and poor periodontal health. Oral hygiene practices are inadequate. Visible plaque, rural residence, and unknown fluoride toothpaste content were associated with higher caries severity. Policy interventions should address preventive care access, sealant provision, fluoride toothpaste availability and labelling, and dietary habits. Future research should examine barriers to oral health behaviours and evaluate intervention effectiveness.

Declarations

Ethics approval: RSU Research Ethics Committee No. 6-1/16/6, 26 November 2020.

Data availability: Data supporting the findings are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Conflicts of interest: None declared.

Author contributions: SEU and IM designed the study. ARP, ES, and US coordinated data collection and clinical examinations. SEU performed statistical analysis and wrote the manuscript. IM supervised the project and provided critical revision. All authors approved the final version.

References

GBD 2017 Oral Disorders Collaborators et al. (2020) 'Global, regional, and national levels and trends in burden of oral conditions from 1990 to 2017: A systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease 2017 study', *Journal of Dental Research*, 99(4), pp. 362–373.

Jasulaityte, L., Veerkamp, J.S. and Weerheijm, K.L. (2007) 'Molar incisor hypomineralization: review and prevalence data from the study of primary school children in Kaunas/Lithuania', *European Archives of Paediatric Dentistry*, 8(2), pp. 87–94.

Kidd, J.B. et al. (2020) 'Evaluation of a national complex oral health improvement programme: a population data linkage cohort study in Scotland', *BMJ Open*, 10(11), e038116.

Maldupa, I. et al. (2020) 'Caries prevalence and severity for 12-year-old children in Latvia', *International Dental Journal*, 71(3), pp. 184–191.

R Core Team (2023) *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. Vienna: R Foundation for Statistical Computing.

Walsh, T. et al. (2019) 'Fluoride toothpastes of different concentrations for preventing dental caries', *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 3, CD007868.

WHO (2013) *Oral Health Surveys: Basic Methods*. 5th edn. Geneva: World Health Organization.

WHO (2023) 'WHO/Europe calls for urgent action on oral disease as highest rates globally are recorded in European Region'. Available at: <https://www.who.int/europe/news/item/20-04-2023> (Accessed: 21 January 2026).

Wickham, H. (2017) *tidyverse: Easily Install and Load the 'Tidyverse'*. R package version 1.2.1.

Wright, J.T. et al. (2016) 'Evidence-based clinical practice guideline for the use of pit-and-fissure sealants', *Journal of the American Dental Association*, 147(8), pp. 672–682.